

EMC2 Annual Report Year 2

December 2025

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Driving Urban Transitions Partnership (DUT)

Project Progress Report

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1. KEY DATA OF THE PROJECT

SHORT TITLE: EMC2

LONG TITLE: The Evolutive Meshed Compact City. A pragmatic transition pathway to the 15-minute City for European metropolitan peripheries.

PROJECT NUMBER: F-DUT-2022-0043

YEAR OF CALL: DUT Call 2022

PROJECT START: 01/10/2023

PROJECT END: 31/10/2026

PROJECT COORDINATOR: Giovanni FUSCO

NUMBER OF REPORT: Annual Report 2

REPORTING PERIOD: from 01/11/2024 to 31/10/2025

1.1 Publishable Project Summary (max. 2 pages) - *only for the Final Project Report*

[INFO: Your text should be easy to read, that is, written in an understandable and accessible way for a broader public. Its purpose should aim to promote the dissemination and support the exploitation of your results. You should refer only to publicly available information and must not include any confidential or personal data (e.g. names and addresses). The Publishable Project Summary must be drafted as a "stand-alone" text. No references should be made to other parts of the report. You may also wish to provide diagrams or photographs illustrating and promoting the work of your project (only as images). Please structure your summary along the following sub-sections:

- *Context and overall objectives*
- *Work performed and main achievements*
- *Results and socio-economic impacts*
- *Policy relevance of your project]*

Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

2. DESCRIPTION OF WORK, OBJECTIVES AND (PRELIMINARY) RESULTS

2.1 Project Progress in the Reporting Period

Is the project progressing as planned and as described in the proposal?

YES

If NO, please explain the reasons therefore in Chapter 2.2 below (deficiencies, risks and bottlenecks).

2.2 Description of Work (max. 3 pages)

- **What are the most important objectives you have accomplished (in line with the ones listed in the Online Survey) in the reporting period?**

- **Please describe the work accomplished in the reporting period, structured according to the work packages. Describe the preliminary innovations and results as indicated in the Online Survey (Product/service/process/policy/social innovations).**
- **Describe how you have worked together with the main target group(s)/stakeholder(s); describe your experiences and key takeaways (please refer to interactions with the urban actors included in the Online Survey).**
- **Describe deficiencies, risks and bottlenecks in the project progress. Describe deviations from the proposed work plan, deliverables and milestones, if any. What helped you or would have helped you to overcome these issues?**

During Year 2, the research project progressed according to plan. In all work packages the targets remain realistically achievable. While no activities were scheduled in WP1 for this project year, work in WP2 and WP3 is well advanced (70% and 90% respectively) and has produced consistent results: in WP2, several workshops were held involving the active partners, and analytical protocols were developed for the identification of main streets, morphological features and connecting links. WP3 has made significant progress in the diachronic analysis of historical street networks and presented its first results in Vienna, in the presence of all research partners and representatives of the City of Vienna, at the symposium "Morphological Perspectives on Urban Outskirts". In WP4, a first model was developed for simulating pedestrian behaviour, as well as methods for assessing green and blue networks within the city. WP5 developed assessment protocols of public space design and for human usage of public space, as well a new 3D method of analysis for modelling linear settlements (UPMSmart). These protocols were implemented comparatively in case studies in several countries. WP6 has been launched and deals with the development of assessment guidelines and a Gen-AI-based analytical protocol. Overall, the results of the second project year show clear methodological and analytical progress in all central thematic areas. These preliminary results have been presented as work in progress at various international conferences, published in conference proceedings, and are currently being prepared for submission to peer-reviewed journals. The progress of the six main work packages (WPs) is detailed below, with some adjustments to the scheduled deliverables.

WP1. Objective: Define the key characteristics of the EMC2 model as a practical application of the 15mC concept in the peripheries of European metropolitan areas, and evaluate the model based on the research project's outcomes.

Status of implementation 70 % (as planned). No work was scheduled in WP1 for the reporting period.

WP2. Objective: Assess the potential of the EMC2 model in the peripheries of selected European metropolitan areas through the implementation of innovative analytical protocols of the street network, of built-up forms, of functions and of accessible population.

Status of implementation: 70% – the objectives formulated in the proposal remain valid, and their achievement is realistic.

The investigations are being carried out in five metropolitan areas: Lille–Roubaix–Tourcoing and the Côte d’Azur, Gothenburg, Vienna and Versilia. The analytical protocol to identify the main streets and the protocol to assess morphological features and functions have been completed. An additional output – the protocol for identifying connecting links within the system – was added to the work plan and has also been completed. Furthermore, the results D2.3, D2.5 and D2.6 are under preparation; completion is expected within the first months of Year 3.

Results and milestones of the period:

- D2.1: Analytical protocol to identify the foreground street network. Completed
- D2.2: Analytical protocol to assess the build-up forms on street networks. Completed
- D2.3: Analytical protocol to assess services on street networks. In progress, completion December 2025

- D2.4: Completed, see Project Report Year 1.
- D2.4b Analytical protocol for identifying connecting links within the system. This is a new result that was added to the original plan: completed.
- D2.5: Maps of results of the application of D 2.1-D2.4. In progress, completion February 2026.
- D2.6: Draft journal paper #3 on combined protocols and comparative analysis Draft journal paper #3 completed but addressing only protocol D2.1, because of its innovative content. A further draft journal paper #3bis for combined protocols and comparative analysis delayed to April 2026.
- M6: Completed Identification of supporting mesh of the EMC2 model in metropolitan areas. In progress, delayed to February 2026.
- M7: Identification of test areas. Achieved.

WP3. Objective: Identify traditional linear settlements within selected European metropolitan areas and understand their historical formation and transformation to assess their capacity to act as starting point of the EMC2 model.

Status of implementation: 90% – the objectives formulated in the proposal remain valid, and their achievement is realistic.

The detailed morphogenetic analysis in Vienna was carried out for 10 selected historical linear settlements. For this purpose, six different time slices were vectorised on the basis of historical maps and aerial photographs, thus documenting the morphological evolution of the settlements. The diachronic analysis of the street networks was carried out for four time points each by SMOG in Vienna and Gothenburg, and by DESTeC in Versilia. In February 2025, a symposium entitled “Morphological Perspectives on Urban Outskirts” took place. Work on D3.5 draft journal paper on historic analysis is ongoing, with completion expected by the end of December 2025.

Results and milestones of the period:

- D3.1: Completed, see Project Report Year 1
- D3.2: Morphogenetic diagram/maps of test areas. Completed
- D3.3: Working paper on diachronic analysis of street networks in Gothenburg and Vienna. Completed
- D3.4: Working paper on assessment of the evolutive potential of test areas. Completed
- D3.5: Draft journal paper on historic analysis. In progress, completion December 2025
- M8: Identification of the evolutionary process behind observed forms in test areas. Achieved

WP4. Objective: Assess the relations of the network of main streets with green/blue networks and with mobility networks.

Status of implementation: 50% – the objectives formulated in the proposal remain valid, and their achievement is realistic.

In France, ESPACE developed a first agent-based model for pedestrian behaviour in a stylized space using the NetLogo platform. A second agent-based model is under development for the test area of Drap (French Riviera), using the vector-based GAMA platform. Simulated scenarios will be further discussed with the French Riviera Planning Agency.

In Sweden, SMOG worked on a review on the influence of morphological parameters on the interaction between humans, focusing on pedestrian movement, and ecosystems in urban green, focusing on biodiversity. This was presented at the International Seminar on Urban Form (ISUF2025) and followed by a recently submitted conference paper. This is the theoretical foundation for the analytical protocol developed for an integrated assessment of the human-nature interaction. The first tests are published in the master thesis “*Multifunctional Suburban Networks*” (master thesis by Charlotta Blom, 2025) and the Social-Ecological Urbanism design studio in Gothenburg, Sweden (2025). In 2026, the complete integrated assessment of planning scenarios in Gothenburg will be finalized.

In Versilia, Italy, DESTeC is nearing completion of the analysis of the set of public and private transport infrastructures— including railway lines and the network of collective road-based connections, with particular reference to terminals, stations, and stops. The network of cycle paths throughout the entire conurbation is also part of this set. Based on these findings, the accessibility of the Turano and Viareggio test areas, selected for the implementation of the EMC2 model, has been assessed.

Results and milestones of the period:

- D 4.1 Analytical protocol of interaction between the EMC2 model and the green/blue networks. Theoretical foundation completed; Analytical protocol 80% completed.
- D 4.2 Maps of assessed potential mobility flows in test areas of Versilia. In progress, completion February 2026.
- D 4.3 Code of the agent-based human behaviour and mobility model in the EMC2. In progress, completion expected December 2025
- D 4.4 Integrated assessment of planning scenarios in Gothenburg with respect to EMC2 and green/blue networks. First test completed; Final assessment 2026.

WP5. Objective: Assess the fine-grained forms and functions of test areas within European metropolitan peripheries and propose possible transformations to implement the EMC2 model.

Status of implementation: 60% – the objectives formulated in the proposal remain valid, and their achievement is realistic.

After developing assessment protocols within Year 1, ESPACE applied them to the test areas of Drap (French Riviera) and Seclin (Lille-Roubaix-Tourcoing). Protocols assess both fine-grained patterns of public space and public-private interfaces and human behaviour on public space. A specific survey of parking use was carried out in Drap. Always in Drap, statistical models were used to cross-analyse urban micro-patterns and human behaviour. Similar analyses will be carried out for Seclin. 3D models are also being developed for the two French test areas.

In Versilia, in the Turano area (Massa), the compliance of the built environment and public spaces with the patterns identified by ESPACE has been assessed, highlighting both specific and overall contexts in which critical issues and misalignments occur. A similar compliance assessment is also underway with regard to the functional layout and the distribution of economic activities—particularly commercial ones—so as to bring to light critical aspects on which design-phase interventions will need to focus. Completion of this work, which will also extend to the Viareggio area, is expected within the first two months of 2026

In Vienna, five different settlements are being investigated, for which a comprehensive historical and current use analysis was prepared. The new analysis method UPMSmart was designed for the modelling of these settlements; it links a 3D model for three different time slices with an underlying database and thus constitutes a City Information Model.

Results and milestones of the period:

- D 5.1 Maps of public/private interfaces, functions and public space organisation of the test areas. Completed in France, in progress in Italy - completion expected in March 2026.
- D 5.2 Ethograms of human usage of test areas in France and correlation with design characteristics. Completed in Drap, completion expected in December 2025 in Seclin.
- D 5.3 Numeric 3D-models of main streets in their present situation. In progress, completion expected in Austria in December 2025, in France in June 2026.
- D 5.6 Draft journal paper #7 on human usage. Completed for the case study of Drap. A second draft journal paper #7bis (3D models) is scheduled for June 2026.
- M9 Fieldwork in test areas. Achieved in Austria and France; in progress in Italy - completion expected in April 2026.

WP6. Objective: Produce assessment and interventions guidelines and assess their compatibility with present regulations. Provide methods to generalize local findings.

Status of implementation: 20% – the objectives formulated in the proposal remain valid, and their achievement is realistic.

Work on WP6 started in summer 2025 and first tackled the development of a Gen-AI-based protocol to generalize the assessments carried out manually in WP5 to wider study areas. This work already resulted in the development of the freely available code of the SAGAI model (Streetscape Assessment through Generative AI), and a first journal paper. Further developments are foreseen for Year 3.

The core of WP6 involves close cooperation between the four research teams and the five urban authorities within the consortium. The drafting of the assessment guidelines after their discussion with urban authorities is in progress.

Results and milestones of the period:

- D 6.1 Document of assessment guidelines of EMC2 potential at metropolitan and local scales. In progress, completion February 2026.
- M10 Validated assessment guidelines of EMC2 potential at metropolitan and local scales. In progress, completion February 2026.

3. IMPACT

3.1 Impact of the Project (*max. 1.5 pages*)

- **What is your project's contribution to urban transitions (societal, economic, cultural and environmental changes) that you would like to highlight as an achievement so far?**
- **How is that linked to the DUT Roadmap¹ and to the DUT Transition Pathway(s)? Please ensure consistency with your answer on *Contribution to the Transition Pathway Missions* in the Online Survey.**
- **What is your project's expected impact in a long-term perspective, both in terms of urban transitions and regarding the DUT Roadmap and the relevant Transition Pathway(s)? Which actions do you plan to take for reaching the expected impact?**

[INFO: Be as concrete as possible, for example: "establishing a good citizen interaction with the urban planning department in terms of gentrification" or "municipality is using a strategy or an app for upkeeping the green in the city".]

The model of the Evolutive Meshed Compact City tackles conjointly the three topics of the 15mC proposed by the DUT call. Even more, it maintains that there is added value in treating the three topics together while recognizing the constraints and opportunities of our networked metropolitan areas. Thus, strengthening the mix of urban functions and services needs morphological (the streetscape potential, with its buildings and their interfaces to the public space) and configurational pre-conditions (the centrality potential of the street network, shaping flows of through-traffic, both pedestrian and vehicular), includes access to transit networks and benefits from attractive public spaces, to be viable over time. By concentrating on main streets, the stronger mix of retail and services within the EMC2 model will produce synergies and increase the attractiveness of the main streets which, by design, will allow for a rich variety of usages by pedestrians, resulting in vibrant public life on the backbone of the surrounding neighborhoods. Our project is linked to the DUT roadmap by identifying and comprehending the spatial synergies between the infrastructures that together make the 15mC work. The protocols developed within the project allow thematic exchange between metropolitan areas, provide common formats and methods and as such contribute to evidence-driven actions and policies.

The project contributes to two of the four Key Areas (KA) identified in the DUT roadmap. First, it contributes to the DUT vision for urban mobility transformation, where traffic planning is integrated into

¹ Document can be found at <https://dutpartnership.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/DUT-Roadmap-2022-komprimiert.pdf>

comprehensive and strategic urban planning and considers different mobility needs. Second, EMC2 starts from the understanding that the built environment fundamentally predetermines mobility options, because all urban movement takes place within the streetscape, which in turn is shaped and defined by buildings and the urban morphology. The protocols developed within EMC2 provide methods to include urban morphology in the decision-making process and evidence-driven action.

By establishing an alternative model for the 15-minute city in European metropolitan peripheries, the project contributes to reach more general goals outlined in the EU Soil Strategy for 2030, or the 11.7 objective of the goal 11 'Make cities inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable' of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): 'provide universal access to safe, inclusive and accessible, green and public spaces, in particular for women and children, older persons and persons with disabilities'. Scaling, replication and mainstreaming of project outcomes, protocols and guidelines, will be instrumental in attaining these ambitious goals (see next section).

Project outcomes are already informing 15mC policies of urban authorities which are part of the EMC2 consortium. In France, the project is helping to reshape how the planning agencies of Nice (AUA) and Lille (ADULM) conceptualise the 15mC, with a renewed emphasis on public space. Discussions with local authorities (Drap, Seclin) are underway to gather more targeted feedback on the research outcomes.

In Italy, the exploration and research activities, carried out in collaboration with the urban planning offices of the municipal administrations, aim to produce results that may help shape the planning strategies of Massa and Viareggio, both of which are currently engaged in drafting their Master Plans.

In Sweden, the municipality of Gothenburg has actively been involved in the design studio at Chalmers, where students work with integrated solutions, implementing the EMC2 model by optimizing the functioning of the main streets in suburban contexts without jeopardizing biodiversity, using the central planning variables network centrality, built density, accessibility and habitat connectivity and functionality.

3.2 Scaling, Replication and Mainstreaming (max. 2 pages) - *only for the Final Project Report*

- **Which of your innovative solutions (product / service / process / policy / social innovations) could be mainstreamed / replicated / scaled-out by cities, businesses or other stakeholders?**
- **Which of these innovative solutions could change citizens' behaviour/mind-sets, and how?**
- **Which of these innovative solutions could make an impact on different governance levels / system level if taken up by policymakers and used for political decisions, new/adapted regulations, etc.?**

[INFO: Think about what your project could possibly achieve within 5-10 years, for example: more integrated transport systems, more localised economies, improved resilience and adaptation to extreme events, inclusive societies with respect to migration and ageing.]

Scaling and replication are central objectives of the project. Analyses are conducted on five distinct European metropolitan areas, each evaluated at different scales (both the entire metropolitan area and targeted peripheral test areas). Scaling concerns both the passage from large scale (the whole metropolitan area) to small scale (test areas in metropolitan peripheries) and, reversely, the generalization from the latter to the former. Replication concerns both the possibility to carry out fine-scale analyses in other peripheral districts, as well as in other European metropolitan areas and peripheral districts not covered by the project.

The protocols developed, along with the EMC2 model as a whole, offer transferable and replicable outcomes. Year 2 of the project particularly contributed to protocol developments, mainly in WP2 (metropolitan scale, identification of foreground street network and its morphological and functional features to assure the role of EMC2 main streets) and WP5 (local scale, identification of patterns of public space, 3D models, assessment of public life), without forgetting more specific contributions from WP3 (historical analysis of urban transformations) and WP4 (interaction with green networks, simulations of pedestrian behaviour). Most of these protocols have been completed by the end of Year 2.

Within WP6, the project will yield a comprehensive specification of the EMC2 model, protocols to assess its application potential at multiple scales, and actionable guidelines for urban practitioners. These guidelines will support the transformation of existing urban and suburban environments. With only minor physical changes, metropolitan authorities will be able to improve internal connectivity and foster compact urban forms along development corridors. Additionally, the protocols will enable the identification of main streets as vectors for this transformation. The production of assessment and intervention guidelines have just started at the end of Year 2 and will be the object of co-construction with urban partners within Year 3. The involvement of urban partners will be fundamental in laying the bases for further mainstreaming of these guidelines in future 15mC policies at different scales.

Another specific contribution to scaling by WP6 is the development of AI-based algorithms to generalize labour-intensive streetscape assessments in test areas within WP5 to larger areas (and ideally city-wide) by the assessment of streetview images. The project has so far laid down the foundational work for such development.

Within all WPs, a particular emphasis has been given to open science and public availability of produced protocols and outcomes within the first two years of the project. Year 3 will further invest the storage of project outcomes (papers, data, maps, algorithms) in freely accessible on-line repositories.

The EMC2 model, along with its analytical protocols and guidelines, holds significant potential for mainstream adoption by local planning authorities. Specifically, collaboration with urban partners in WP6 will evaluate the intervention guidelines in relation to current regulations, identifying potential barriers to broader implementation. Dissemination and outreach activities will further support this general objective. However, given the project's research-oriented nature, validation of the EMC2 model takes precedence over mainstreaming its guidelines. A subsequent, innovation-focused project may be necessary to address mainstream integration within planning practices more directly.

3.3 Interdisciplinarity / Transdisciplinarity (max. 0.5 page)

Did any new insights arise because of the interdisciplinary or transdisciplinary setup of your project?

[INFO: For example: using a methodology from another discipline; engaging non-academic partners, e.g. civil society, local governance, or business actors, in project activities / tasks]

The project consortium consists of four public research units (ESPACE, SMOG, DESTeC, and TUW-UD) and four public urban authorities (the Cities of Gothenburg and Viareggio, in Sweden and Italy, and the planning agencies AUA and ADULM in France). Additionally, a fifth public authority, the city of Massa in Italy, has joined the consortium in Year 2.

The research units represent diverse countries and disciplinary fields—geography, urban planning and design, civil engineering, and architecture. Each has a specific focus: Urban Design - TUW specializes in architecture and urban design; ESPACE in geography and planning; DESTeC in engineering and planning; and SMOG in urban design and planning. Despite these distinct disciplines, all units share a foundational interest in urban morphology, supporting interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration. This morphological perspective is similarly valued by the public authorities involved in the consortium.

Several methodologies act as additional bridges between the research units. Configurational approaches rooted in network analysis are key focal points for SMoG (Sweden) and DESTeC (Italy). Geoprocessing in urban analysis is a defining feature of ESPACE (France) and is also shared by SMoG and DESTeC. Historical urban morphology, a central focus for Urban Design - TUW, resonates through more general morphological research across the other three units. Urban 3D-modeling is a further common area of interest between UD-TUW and ESPACE, even if with different methodological approaches. Year 2 of the project has been characterised by outstanding trans-disciplinary and trans-national cooperations:

- ESPACE and DU-TUW collaborated on catalogues of historical linear settlements and in design studios. They also identified 3D modelling as object of further methodological comparison.
- DU-TUW and SMoG collaborated in the joint analysis of centrality shift and morphological transformations in Vienna.
- SMoG and ESPACE jointly developed new protocols to detect multi-scale foreground networks in suburban areas.
- ESPACE and DESTeC coordinated their fieldwork on test areas and the application of the same protocols of public space assessment.

Regular transdisciplinary meetings have been held across various work packages (within Year 2 this was the case for WP2, WP3, and WP5). Conducted primarily online, these meetings enable consortium members to collaboratively address the multifaceted aspects of each work package, drawing on the consortium's combined expertise and diverse disciplinary knowledge.

Important interactions also happened in person. Two young researchers from UD-TUW and DESTeC were hosted by ESPACE for two weeks in October 2024, to compare approaches in WP5 and acquire new skills in methods of urban analysis based on pattern languages. L. Spieck (UD-TUW) later worked as trainee at ESPACE and ADULM (February-June 2025) to assess the test area of Seclin, and later worked at intervention proposals back at UD-TUW (work in progress). UD-TUW organized a WP3 symposium in Vienna (February 2025), where participants from the four research groups gathered to interact and advance in their research agenda.

Additionally, during the second year, meetings were organized between urban public authorities and academic members, mainly on a national level (e.g., ESPACE with AUA and ADULM; SMoG with the city of Gothenburg; DESTeC with the cities of Viareggio and Massa). These interactions facilitated the exchange of academic research and professional practice with a shared understanding of the national regulatory framework.

3.4 Experiences from Experimental Approaches, like ULL (if applicable) *(max. 1 page)*

Describe your activities and experiences from experimental approaches, like Urban Living Labs (ULL), that can facilitate the co-design of radical transitions towards greater liveability in urban areas. How did you engage different target groups, such as local public administrations and residents, businesses, NGOs, civil society organisations, and more?

The EMC2 project did not implement any experimental approaches in the first two years beyond conducting fieldwork on the test areas of WP3, WP4, and WP5. During the first two years, the Urban Design team at TUW, the ESPACE team at Université Côte d'Azur and the SMoG team at Chalmers TU organized teaching and research studios. In Vienna, they involved master students of architecture in November 2023-January 2024, in April-June 2024 and in November 2024-January 2025 at TUW, with the participation of urban actors (city of Vienna, the professional association IG Architektur) and of members of ESPACE from France. In Nice, they involved master students in geography and international master students in engineering of smart cities, in october-november 2023, 2024 and 2025. In Gothenburg,

Sweden, the 2025 Social-Ecological Urbanism design studio at Chalmers TU focused on issues of green infrastructure within the 15mC.

These experimental activities were instrumental both in gaining new inputs and insights for the EMC2 project and to start disseminating this new 15mC model among the future generation of urban practitioners.

In France, ESPACE and the Planning Agencies AUA and ADULM engaged in two seminars (June 2024, February 2025). Further informal meetings were held with planners from the city of Seclin, the test area of the project in the Lille-Roubaix-Tourcoing metropolitan area.

In Italy, DESTeC and the City of Massa engaged in a series of participatory sessions with local residents, carried out as a key component of the participatory planning process for the Municipal Structural Plan, during which the "15-minute city" concept was explored. Furthermore, internal meetings were held between DESTeC and the City of Viareggio to discuss the 15-minute city concept and identify a possible test area within the municipal boundaries.

In Sweden, a workshop was held between SMoG researchers, City of Gothenburg and the City and Regional Public Transit Agencies on integration of public transport on the urban street network.

Outcomes from WP3, WP4, and WP5 could foster greater engagement with local urban stakeholders beyond those already participating in the consortium. Researchers will assess opportunities for collaboration in this direction in Year 3.

However, experimental approaches such as urban living labs were not part of the original research proposal and would require additional human resources. A future, innovation-focused project on the EMC2 model could pave the way for deeper involvement in urban living labs.

4. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Please describe in what way you promoted dissemination and implementation of the results to the scientific community, policymakers, urban actors as well as citizens/general public and in what way you created new market opportunities?

4.1 Description of dissemination / communication activities (max. 1.5 pages)

Highlight your most important dissemination or communication activities (1 to 3 activities) and how they have contributed to achieving your project goals in more detail. Write the text as a short story:

- **Introduction**
- **What has been done concretely?**
- **Result(s) from these actions**

[INFO: If applicable, please include information on the following: Type of activity (see activity types below), website/social media page used, target group(s), number of participants, aim of the activity, what are the main takeaways or resulting effects, describe any impact from your activity obtained through follow-up you did (media reach, feedback, change in perspectives, attitudes, type of users, etc.), next steps or a lesson learned.]

The scientific dissemination and the communication (outreach) of project outcomes outside of the perimeter of the consortium is the specific objective of WP7 (not dealt with in section 2.2).

Status of implementation 60% (as scheduled).

As for communication, consortium members kept on feeding the website of the project (<https://emc2-dut.org/>). 2 consortium members participated in the DUT annual event in Milan (September 30th-October 1st 2025). One article was published on The Conversation France (<https://theconversation.com/peut-on-faire-une-ville-du-quart-dheure-dans-le-periurbain-257079>). A shorter version of this test was produced for the Université Côte d'Azur newsletter Intervalle (May 2025).

Within the project, UD-TUW organised the "Linear Settlement Symposium" (January 27-28 2025) with urban actors (City of Vienna), bachelor and master students at TUW, with the participation of members from CNRS-ESPACE. A wider initiative was the international symposium held in Vienna on February 20th-21st 2025: "Morphological Perspectives on Urban Outskirts". The initiative articulated a scientific workshop for the 15 participating members of the consortium and an outreach initiative of public dissemination, with the participation of the city of Vienna (K. Hofstätter from the magistrate MA50), M. Jäger for the 15mC TP of DUT, other DUT Partnership projects at TU Wien (DREAMS, MDB15) and the Austrian Academy of Sciences (AccessCity4All). 8 posters were produced for this event.

The consortium became involved in the activities of the DUT Knowledge Hub on the 15mC, with two young researchers — A. Araldi in France and F. Mara in Italy — representing the EMC2 consortium within the Hub. G. Fusco also took part in the working group on shared scientific valorisation for the 2022 cohort, led by M. Jäger.

Consortium members also participated in other initiatives not specifically organized within the project:

G. Fusco held an invited conference at ENA-INAU-Centre Jacques Berque (Rabat, Morocco) on a pattern language for the convivial 15mC.

G. Fusco gave a presentation at "La ville nouveaux horizons 2025", an outreach event organised by Le Point magazine on issues of urban planning and design in France.

A. Psenner gave lecture with the title: "EMC2 – The Evolutive Meshed Compact City. Ideen zur Reorganisation von Stadtrandlagen" at: Freiheit oder Zwang? Mobilität und Alltag jenseits der Stadt Symposium, Universität Liechtenstein (25.10.2025)

I. Ellenbroek gave a presentation at the international seminar "Tracing Sustainable Urban River Space Transformations" (Leiden, The Netherlands, 7-11 April 2025) on data, methods and tools for social-ecological integration.

V. Cutini, F. Mara, C. Anselmi, and F. Deri presented the preliminary results of their research activities at the the SIU (Italian Urban Planning Society) conference held in Milan from 18 to 20 June 2025.

As for scientific dissemination in international conferences, the consortium decided to focus on a limited number of international events within year 2: ISUF 2025 (International Seminar on Urban Form, Turin June 17-20 2025), ICCSA 2025 (International Conference of Computer Science and its Applications, Istanbul June 30-July 3 2025) and ECTQG 2025 (European Colloquium of Theoretical and Quantitative Geography, Tallinn Sept 10-14 2025). The DESTeC team also participated in the Input Conference (Pavia, 6-8 Sept 2025), an Italian conference with international audience.

The consortium involvement in ISUF 2025 was particularly important. Beyond the 6 presentations, G. Fusco and M. Berghauser Pont also took part in the roundtable "Urban morphology and common engagement", to present the morphological challenges of the 15mC with respect to the EMC2 project.

9 papers/long abstracts were published within the conference proceedings:

Anselmi C., Mara F., Deri F. (2025) Big-data Reliability in Informing the 15-Minute City Modelling: a Comparison between OpenStreetMap and Google Maps. In O. Gervasi et al. (Eds.): ICCSA 2025 Workshops Proceedings, LNCS 15892, p. 325–341. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-97638-4_21

Cutini V. (2025) Islands or bridges? 15-minute cities and weak ties. In O. Gervasi et al. (Eds.): ICCSA 2025 Workshops Proceedings, LNCS 15892, p. 311–324, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-97638-4_20

Deri F., Anselmi C., Mara F. (2025) The configuration of urban form: Morphogenetic and Configurational Analysis for Identifying 15-Minutes City Opportunities for Densification. ISUF – Proceedings of ISUF 2025 (in press)

Deri F., Mara F., Anselmi C., Mara F. (2025) Crowdsourced Data for Urban Planning: A Critical Evaluation of OpenStreetMap Accuracy and Completeness. In O. Gervasi et al. (Eds.): ICCSA 2025 Workshops Proceedings, LNCS 15897, p. 403–420, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-97660-5_27

Ellenbroek, Stavroulaki, Berghauer Pont (2025). A review on the influence of morphological parameters on the interaction between humans and ecosystems in urban green spaces. Proceedings of ISUF 2025 (in press)

Fusco G., Picard G., 2025, Assessing Form Patterns for the Suburban 15-Minute City: The Case of Drap (France). Proceedings of ISUF 2025 (in press)

Loeschenbrand, D., Tobisch, S.T., Psenner, A. (2025) UPMsmart – qualitative street space analysis on large-scale. Proceedings of ISUF 2025 (in press)

Perez J., Fusco G., 2025, Assessing urban scenes for the 15-minute city through SAGAI (Streetscape Analysis with Generative AI). ECTQG 2025 – Programme + Book of Abstracts, Tallinn University of Technology ISBN 978-9949-584-23-9, p. 128-129.

Stavroulaki, I., D. Löschenbrand, S. Tobisch, T. Hellsten Romeborn, A. Psenner, M. Berghauer Pont (2025). The role of network centrality shifts for local morphological transformations. A case study of 13 linear settlements in the metropolitan area of Vienna. Proceedings of ISUF 2025 (in press)

The first 4 papers were published on internationally recognized scientific journals, two more have been drafted but not submitted to publication yet:

Mara F., Anselmi C., Deri F. (2025) Urban Systems, When They Conurbate: The Diachronic-configurational approach to detect The Shifting of Centrality in Versilia, *Urban Design International*, DOI: [10.1057/s41289-025-00272-9](https://doi.org/10.1057/s41289-025-00272-9)

Mara F., Anselmi C., Deri F., Cutini V. (2025) The divergent geographies of urban amenities: a data comparison between OpenStreetMap and Google Maps, *Sustainability* 2025, 17, 9016 <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/17/20/9016>

Perez J., Fusco G., 2025, Streetscape Analysis with Generative AI (SAGAI): Vision-Language Assessment and Mapping of Urban Scenes, *Geomatica*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomat.2025.100063>

Perez J., Fusco G., 2025, Population potential on catchment area (PPCA): A Python-based tool for worldwide geospatial population analysis, *SoftwareX*, 31(102245), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2025.102245>

Also in Year 2, consortium members were specifically engaged in organising teaching modules for graduate students. The aim is to prepare future professionals to use the methods and approaches developed by EMC2 for creating pedestrian-friendly 15mC environments.

A design studio and an elective seminar were organised by UD-TUW (1st semester 2024-25) concluded by the Linear Settlement Symposium (January 27-28 2025).

A Social-Ecological Urbanism Studio 2025 was organised by SMOG at Chalmers University of Technology.

A design studio was organised by ESPACE at Université Côte d’Azur for French-speaking graduate students (October-November 2025), as well an urban analysis workshop concluded by an urban walk for English-speaking students of the MSc Engineers for Smart Cities (September-October 2025).

In Italy, as part of the Urban Analysis and Planning Laboratory of the Master's Degree Programme in Building Engineering–Architecture, specific in-depth workshops were carried out on the distribution of economic and service activities within the territories of various Tuscan municipalities, in order to interpret the presence and settlement dynamics of proximity-based activities

Deliverables of the period:

D 7.2 Communication initiative carried out in Austria (Vienna, February 2025 – more communication events are forthcoming in Year 3 for France, Italy and Sweden)

4.2 Provide statistical data on your dissemination / communication activities

In reference to chapter 4.1, please specify the (estimated) number of dissemination and communication activities linked to your project for each of the following categories. For the evaluation it is important that you only enter numbers:

Communication activities

- Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.): 4
- Exhibition: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Interview: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Media article: 2
- Newsletter : Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Print materials (brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.): 9 (1 DUT event + 8 Vienna Symposium)
- Social media : Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- TV / radio campaign: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Press release: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Other communication activities: Website of the project (<https://emc2-dut.org/>)

Dissemination activities

- Clustering activities: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Collaboration with EU-funded projects: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Conferences: Participation to 3 international scientific conferences (ISUF 2025, ICCSA 2025 and ECTQG 2025) and 1 national conference (INPUT 2025) with 11 presentations and 9 proceedings papers.
- Education and training events: organization of 5 teaching modules t (2 TUWien, 2 Université Côte d'Azur, 1 Chalmers University of Technology).
- Meetings: organization of 1 group discussion (CNRS-ESPACE/AUA/ADULM February 2025) between researchers and urban actors, 1 symposium open to local actors (Vienna, January 2025) and 1 international symposium (Vienna, february 2025), participation to 5 workshops/meetings (France, Morocco, Lichtenstein, Netherlands, Italy).
- Other scientific collaboration: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

Specify the (estimated) number of persons reached, in the context of all dissemination and communication activities, in each of the following categories:

- Industry, business partners: 10 (within the IMREDD Institute of Innovation and Partnership of Université Côte d'Azur, France).
- Innovators: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Investors: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- EU Institutions: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

- National authorities: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Regional authorities: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Local authorities: 8
- Civil society: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Citizens: 100 (participants to the symposia in Vienna, January 2025 and February 2025)
- Research communities: Participation to 3 international scientific conferences and 1 national scientific conference (ISUF 2025, ICCSA 2025, ECTQG 2025, INPUT 2025) reaching app. 350 people.
- Specific end user communities: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.): Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.
- Other: Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

5. OUTLOOK (max. 1 page)

Only for annual reports:

Describe the work planned for the next reporting period, structured according to the work packages. Discuss envisaged changes as compared to the original work plan, if any, reflecting the deficiencies, risks and bottlenecks described in Chapter 2.2.

Only for final reports:

➤ Follow-up Investments and Opportunities

Based on your previous responses in the Online Survey (under *Follow-up Activities*), how has your participation in the DUT Partnership:

- **Facilitated further investments or funding opportunities to expand your project activities?**
- **Created follow-up opportunities with new partners, organisations, or networks?**
- **Opened new perspectives or innovative approaches that could help transform urban areas?**

➤ Impact on Future Research and Innovation (R&I) Work

What has been the most beneficial impact of participating in the DUT Partnership on your future research and innovation work? Please consider aspects, such as:

- **Enhanced knowledge, expertise, or capacity-building for future projects.**
- **New collaborations, partnerships, or networks that have emerged.**
- **Any other significant outcomes that you attribute to your involvement with the DUT Partnership.**

The third year of the research project will be its final. The working plan has two main goals: finalize all the open research tasks and fully engage in the dissemination/communication of the research outcomes. All WPs will be concluded, whether they are already fully advanced (WP1, WP2, WP3, WP5), at mid-way (WP4) or just started (WP6). The main adjustment to the original timeline will be the extension of WP2 until month 28. A detailed breakdown of the planned activities for each WP is provided below.

WP1 will engage in a final validation/modification of the EMC2 model and its assessment criteria, with the hindsight of the research outcomes of WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 and the feedback from collaboration with urban authorities in WP6.

WP2 accumulated some delay on the original program, but will be finalized within February 2026, with the completion of the analytical protocol to assess services on street networks, the production of a set of maps applying the different analytical protocols on the five metropolitan areas of the project and the

production of a new draft journal paper, combining protocols and proposing a comparative analysis of the case studies. Deliverables and Milestones scheduled for year 3:

- D2.3: Analytical protocol to assess services on street networks. In progress, completion December 2025.
- D2.5: Maps of results of the application of D 2.1-D2.4. In progress, completion February 2026.
- D2.6: Draft journal paper #3bis for combined protocols and comparative analysis, April 2026.
- M6: Completed Identification of supporting mesh of the EMC2 model in metropolitan areas. In progress, completion February 2026.

WP3 is almost completed. Within the first two months of year 3 consortium members will finalize its last deliverable :

- D3.5: Draft journal paper on historic analysis. In progress, completion December 2025

WP4 will achieve important developments during Year 3 and arrive to its conclusion.

In France, ESPACE will finalize the development of the agent-based model of pedestrian behaviour in the test area of Drap within December 2025 and later work at simulating and assessing different scenarios of organization of the public space of Drap.

In Sweden, SMOG will finalize the analytical protocol of interaction between the EMC2 model and the green/blue networks as well as the Integrated assessment of planning scenarios in Gothenburg. This will also lead to the journal paper #5 on the interaction between the EMC2 model and the green/blue networks.

In Italy, DESTeC will carry out an analysis of the network of green infrastructures present in the Versilia conurbation for the beginning of the third year. This will be integrated with the collection of areas currently subject to landscape protection under the Tuscany Regional Landscape Plan, so as to enable the determination of the interactions between the blue and green networks and the study areas.

Deliverables and milestones scheduled for Year 3:

- D 4.1 Analytical protocol of interaction between the EMC2 model and the green/blue networks. February 2026.
- D 4.2 Maps of assessed potential mobility flows in test areas of Versilia. January 2026.
- D 4.3 Code of the agent-based human behaviour and mobility model in the EMC2. In progress, completion expected December 2025
- D 4.4 Integrated assessment of planning scenarios in Gothenburg with respect to EMC2 and green/blue networks. June 2026.
- D 4.5 Working paper on assessment of planning scenarios for the French Riviera through model simulations. April 2026.
- D 4.6 Draft journal paper #5 on the interaction between the EMC2 model and the green/blue networks. September 2026.
- D 4.7 Draft journal paper #6 on interaction EMC2 and pedestrian mobility. June 2026.
- M11 Completed specification of EMC2 w.r.t. interaction with multi-modal mobility system. June 2026.
- M12 Completed specification of the EMC2 model concerning the interaction with ecological networks. June 2026.

WP5 is almost finalized in Austria and France, while it will be further developed in Italy. In France, the public space assessment and the ethograms of public space usage have been completed in Drap and Seclin. Only a statistical cross-analysis still needs to be carried out for the latter. The 3D models will be further developed to visualise the patterns already assessed. Project proposals will also be prepared and discussed with urban stakeholders.

In Austria, 3D models of the UPMSmart type will be finalized for the four test areas of Leopoldau, Großjedlersdorf, Untersievering and Simmering.

In Italy, fieldwork and public space assessment will be concluded in Turano (Massa) and Aurelia Sud sector (Viareggio). Once the analysis of the morphological, configurational, and functional aspects that diverge from the model has been completed (scheduled for the early months of 2026), the design phase aimed at implementing EMC2 in the two cases of Massa and Viareggio will begin. Project proposal will be developed integrating the existing planning constraints.

Results and milestones of the period:

- D 5.1 Maps of public/private interfaces, functions and public space organisation of the test areas. Completed in France and Austria, in progress in Italy - completion expected in April 2026.
- D 5.2 Ethograms of human usage of test areas in France and correlation with design characteristics. Completed in Drap, completion expected in December 2025 in Seclin.
- D 5.3 Numeric 3D-models of main streets in their present situation. In progress, completion expected in Austria in December 2025, in France in June 2026.
- D 5.4 Numeric 3D-models of main streets for future scenarios. July 2026.
- D 5.5 Project proposal for the test area in Versilia. July 2026.
- D 5.6 A second draft journal paper #7bis (3D models) is scheduled for June 2026.
- M9 Fieldwork in test areas. Achieved in Austria and France; in progress in Italy - completion expected April 2026.
- M13 3D digital models and project proposals completed and assessed. July 2026.

WP6 was scheduled to be carried out mainly in Year 3. The production of assessment and intervention guidelines will take the form of a pattern language that bridges scales and domains of analysis. The intervention guidelines will also take regulatory aspects into account. These guidelines will be produced in close collaboration with the consortium's urban partners. In parallel, the Gen-AI-based protocol designed to generalise the assessments carried out manually in WP5 will be completed and evaluated by researchers at ESPACE.

Deliverables and milestones of the period:

- D 6.1 Document of assessment guidelines of EMC2 potential at metropolitan and local scales. In progress, completion February 2026.
- D 6.2 Document of intervention guidelines to implement the EMC2 model, also highlighting regulatory constraints and other institutional obstacles. July 2026.
- D 6.3 Improved assessment method of EMC2 using AI. October 2026.
- D 6.4 Draft journal paper #8 on policy relevance of guidelines. October 2026.
- M10 Validated assessment guidelines of EMC2 potential at metropolitan and local scales. In progress, completion February 2026.
- M14 Validated intervention guidelines to implement the EMC2 model, considering regulatory constraints. July 2026.

In **WP7**, consortium members will continue their efforts in the scientific dissemination of research outcomes (participation in international conferences, publication of articles in scientific journals, and the upload of research papers, data, and maps to open repositories, in line with the Data Management Plan and an open-science approach). Involvement in the activities of the DUT Knowledge Hub on the 15mC will be continued. Year 3 will also be marked by the organisation of three communication events aimed at the professional planning community in France, Italy, and Sweden (D7.3–7.4, 7.5).

6. PROJECT ORGANISATION AND MANAGEMENT *(no page limit)*

Please provide information on coordination activities during the reporting period, such as communication between project participants, possible cooperation with other projects etc.

Have changes occurred in terms of project organisation and management in the reporting period?

NO

Within the project organization, a transversal work package (WP8) has the objective to ensure efficient management of the project. The first year was marked by significant efforts in establishing both the administrative and scientific infrastructure. Project management was much smoother in Year 2. Specifically, within Year 2:

- Two General Assemblies were convened on December 19th 2024 and June 16th 2025.
- The consortium integrated the City of Massa (Italy) as cooperation partner, following the decision of the Dec 19th 2024 General Assembly.
- Steering Committee meetings were held on an almost monthly basis (Oct 23rd, Nov 28th and Dec 16th 2024, Jan 30th, Feb 21st, March 17th, Apr 23rd, May 20th, June 20th, July 7th, Sept 4th, Nov 27th 2025).

A further milestone at the end of Year 2 was the drafting of the second version of the Data Management Plan (November 2025).

Regarding research infrastructure, consortium members keep on using the shared platform for project data and documents on CNRS's Humanum platform, providing a secure, high-capacity shared space (Sharedocs) accessible through credentials.

In terms of human resources, year 2 saw the recruitment of 3 postdoctoral researcher (at ESPACE-CNRS and at DESTeC, 33% women) and 2 interns (at ESPACE-CNRS, 100% women). All 6 PhD candidates were recruited in year 1 (at ESPACE-CNRS/AUA, DESTeC, SMoG, and UD-TUW, 67% women).

A specific difficulty the Consortium must manage throughout the project is a slight misalignment in the official start dates. Administratively and financially, the project began on October 1st, 2023, for partners in Austria and Sweden, but on November 1st, 2023, for partners in France and Italy.

7. YOUR COMMENTS FOR THE DUT PARTNERSHIP *(no page limit)*

Do you have any comments for the DUT Partnership?

Klicken oder tippen Sie hier, um Text einzugeben.

8. ELECTRONIC SIGNATURE

This report is fully agreed among all partners of the project.

Date: 01.12.2025

Name of coordinator: Giovanni FUSCO

9. FORMALITIES CHECKLIST

- All sections of this reporting template must be filled in and answered.
- Please submit the Project Progress Report / Final Project Report in .pdf format via the Online Project Monitoring System accessible at: <https://ffg.countit.at/#/login>
- In case of questions with regard to this reporting template, please send an email to the **Projects Contact Point:** projects@dutpartnership.eu

 Please note that you can only fill in the form fields, all other content is blocked. For automatic evaluation purposes, please ensure that you submit the report as a **Word document**. You can submit a pdf in addition.